

Sample Name: 10mM 2

dCMP
dCMP

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Acq. Operator   : SYSTEM                               Seq. Line :    2
Acq. Instrument : Cornelius                           Location  :   22
Injection Date  : 1/20/2022 2:32:09 PM                Inj       :    1
                                                    Inj Volume: 50.000 µl

Acq. Method     : C:\Chem32\2\Data\WNL\WNL_template 2022-01-20 14-04-27\Phenomenex C18 Run
                  25mins nucleotides.M
Last changed    : 1/20/2022 2:36:00 PM by SYSTEM
                  (modified after loading)
Analysis Method : C:\Chem32\2\Data\WNL\WNL_template 2022-01-20 14-04-27\Phenomenex C18 Run
                  25mins nucleotides.M (Sequence Method)
Last changed    : 1/20/2022 4:06:35 PM by SYSTEM
                  (modified after loading)
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External Standard Report
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Sorted By      :      Signal
Multiplier     :      1.0000
Dilution      :      1.0000
Do not use Multiplier & Dilution Factor with ISTDs
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Area Percent Report
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Sorted By      :      Signal
Multiplier     :      1.0000
Dilution      :      1.0000
Do not use Multiplier & Dilution Factor with ISTDs

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Signal 1: DAD1 F, Sig=254,4 Ref=off

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	1.945	BV	0.0566	8.06002	2.20994	0.2397
2	2.014	VV	0.0734	19.42439	3.81745	0.5776
3	2.097	VB	0.0576	20.43744	5.47327	0.6077
4	2.273	BV	0.1047	68.55166	8.81802	2.0385
5	2.422	VV	0.0988	57.33479	8.08265	1.7049
6	2.599	VB	0.0872	11.66396	1.85903	0.3468
7	2.824	BV	0.0618	8.47182	2.15706	0.2519
8	2.949	VB	0.0720	29.92152	6.23393	0.8898
9	3.329	BV	0.0793	30.68998	6.03416	0.9126
10	3.532	VV	0.0891	146.11876	24.65940	4.3450
11	4.054	VB	0.0985	23.91818	3.64650	0.7112
12	4.508	BV	0.0850	11.08661	1.98976	0.3297
13	4.653	VV R	0.1149	69.88439	9.16747	2.0781
14	5.152	BB	0.1222	9.59328	1.26863	0.2853
15	6.156	BB	0.1859	28.13345	2.34581	0.8366
16	7.997	BB	0.1802	165.54008	14.18040	4.9226
17	8.750	BB	0.2007	75.71417	5.86269	2.2515
18	9.702	BB	0.2591	64.58152	3.56868	1.9204
19	11.124	BB	0.2759	258.98688	14.39644	7.7013
20	14.952	BB	0.4184	809.94934	28.77006	24.0849
21	19.118	BB	0.4456	262.35522	8.85765	7.8015
22	21.900	BB	0.3422	641.46875	28.33003	19.0749
23	24.801	BB	0.2414	541.00336	34.05280	16.0875

Totals : 3362.88960 225.78183

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*** End of Report ***